

DIFFERENT STRATEGIES OF TEACHING ACADEMIC VOCABULARY FOR EFL LEARNERS

Utaganova Roza Mamadiyor qizi

Jizzakh State Pedagogical University

rozautaganova9988@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Today, English language has been playing an important role in different disciplines in both academic and daily life in order to communicate orally or in a written discourse throughout the world. Not only learning English itself, but also acquiring any kinds of foreign language requires to know plethora of vocabularies in both academic and casual style to convey the message in spoken and written discourse. Specifically, academic vocabulary learning is one of the most valuable aspects of learning language in terms of using in different programs or subjects. Nation (2001) states that being aware of academic vocabulary and ability to comprehend and being able to implement it in writing is an important tool for students in English for Academic Purpose (EAP) programs. In this work, different strategies and various methods, tools, and approaches are discussed about how to teach ESP vocabulary for different age group of people.

Key words: EAP learners, ESP learners, academic vocabulary, English Teaching as a foreign language, teaching English as second language, vocabulary

In different education contexts, general and academic vocabulary are considered so as to be encountered and used in students' writing according to studies (Yan & Staples, 2017; Csomay & Prades, 2018; Durrant, 2016) which can have an impact on future teaching and learning practices through the improvement of vocabulary lists (Csomay & Petrovic, 2012).

The purpose of this paper is analyzing and learning the difficulties of acquiring and implementing of academic vocabularies through variety of methods or strategies by reviewing significant literature related to the academic vocabulary for students who use the language for EAP programs and use in an academic writing. At the same time, the research paper gives relevant definitions and certain factors which needed to take an account while learning and teaching academic vocabulary in this paper. Furthermore, it demonstrates certain common strategies that are usually used and discusses different ways of teaching vocabularies and valuable recommendations to learn and teach them. Additionally, I think that this paper will be useful for my students

for academic words usage in formal writing and I want to use it in my future teaching career in education not only for English learners, but also for EAP learners.

The large scope of review defines key terms such as ‘vocabulary’, ‘academic vocabulary’, and some similar or controversial ideas related to them through paragraphs.

When it comes to the term ‘vocabulary’, Cambridge Advanced Learner’s Dictionary (2008) states that vocabulary, is a word that a particular individual knows and uses, those all words also in a particular language or subject. Similarly, Hatch and Brown (1995) say that vocabulary is a specific set of words, which a person is aware of it and can use in a language. It is usually considered that vocabulary is a bit straightforward term to understand, as it is clear, concise, and slightly easy to use. However, it is defined in another way, saying vocabulary includes not only single words but also multiword phrases, idioms, and even sentences. The term lexis is being used which refers the whole vocabulary items (Barcroft, Sunderman & Schmitt, 2011). Furthermore, actually, there are different kinds of vocabulary (specialized/non-specialized, academic/general, receptive/productive, active/passive) and each of them has their own definitions. Learning these words is the aspect that makes the linguistic knowledge significant (Nusha M. & Janebzedah H., 2016). What is more, EFL teachers should teach their students how to use the words properly and in relevant context.

Obviously, in teaching and learning a foreign language, it is necessary to know the difference or similarity between the expressions “vocabulary” and “academic vocabulary”. “Vocabulary” is a general and large-scale term, which includes different types of lexemes. ‘Academic vocabulary’ is usually known as ‘useful scientific vocabulary, sub-technical or semi-technical vocabulary, specialized non-technical lexis, and frame words (Nation, 2001), the words which is used in academic discourse both in spoken or written version and they can be used in different disciplines. For example, ‘girl, bike or beautiful’ can be easily understood as they are not complicated, but the words such as ‘discipline, accumulate’ should be learned through instruction as they have different meanings and usage of context, specifically, in academic writing or researches.

As far as the importance of academic vocabulary concerned, there are many reasons for to learn and teach them. Firstly, it is needed in ‘an academic career’ (Hyland & Tse, 2007), secondly, it is helpful to ‘read and understand texts from different disciplines which is related to the academic vocabulary knowledge’ (Nagy & Townsend, 2012).

Nation (2001) also says that learning academic words are essential, particularly, in professional settings. For instance, medical student does not knows about what ‘analysis’ is, the life can be lost. Another important reason why learning ‘academic

words are vital is that they can play a crucial role as an intellectual tool to encourage students' critical thinking, problem solving and decision making skills (2009)'. To conclude, academic vocabulary deserves better learning as it is essential both in education and in life.

There are some issues on learning academic vocabulary, as it is not used in 'conversational or social texts' (Aldawsari H. 2017), especially in the beginning of the 2L learning, therefore, learners may have just minimal opportunities to use and memorize them effectively. Also Adawsari (2017) states that academic vocabulary has an abstract nature: so, learners can not use a full range of effective vocabulary.

At the same time, lots of learners are taught for words in an inactive way, just context reading or experiencing them in an indirect way. The learners for those who want to learn more usually do not satisfy with these types of learning manners. For EFL learners,

Nushi (2016) states that vocabulary knowledge can be gained through games, scenarios and activities in order to learn the words both in an implicit and explicit way.

However, lots of EFL learners find academic vocabulary difficult to learn. As Adawsari, Dobelmann and Stern (2009) also say that the reason for the difficulty is that not repeated the words in the everyday life. The solution to the problems could be the effort made by EFL teachers, implementing new and effective techniques, strategies, and tools which can develop students' academic vocabulary skills.

There are different types of strategies to teach Academic vocabulary to the students. They include traditional approaches, techniques, new strategies as well as modern and technological methods. As for academic vocabulary learning, there are some techniques based on activities, considered as simple to learn, remember, and use them. Nushi and Janebzedah (2005) state that activities are differ from each other as they are used in different parts of the lessons such as pre-reading, while - reading, and post-reading, which can help actively to enhance academic vocabulary (p.55). Moreover, they point out that in these types of strategies, the lessons are student-centered as they make discussions and the teacher may not make much effort. However, Nushi also admit that this method would not be effective, if the resources or materials are not appropriate (p.58).

Although Nushi (2016) states that students need to learn in an interactive way rather than learning them just in context, Lawson and Hogben (1996) say that it is easy to learn and memorize words in texts, considering vocabulary in a 'network of meaning'(p.131-135). Because of this, the primary reason may be there are lots of reading passages in vocabulary books. Students should learn academic vocabulary with the real examples such as the sources teachers are using should be authentic and related to real life. As a result, students may satisfy with their studying and set of words they

learned. Nushi and Janebzeda (2016) also say that learning vocabulary with in groups could be better as they are straightforward to memorize and use them correctly (p.55)

In fact, there are different types of methods, activities and strategies for teaching academic vocabulary, additionally, as we are living in a technological-advanced world, teachers can use ‘technology’ to teach academic words in an effective way. Nushi and Janebzedah say that there are lots of advantages of computers or online tools as they can be used to present new topic, using PowerPoint slides and students also exchange their knowledge with their fellows. However, Selvester (2012) states that Computer Assisted Language Learning (CALL) methods could be tricky to apply, as they may have problems related to use them properly. At the same time, using computers and online tools can be engaging and intriguing for students and there are different types of online dictionaries, websites, and resources, not only for teaching, but also for self-studying.

Furthermore, there are another way of learning academic vocabulary with a help of teacher, but also by students themselves. Johns (2002) shows that a technique ‘Data-driven learning (DDL)’ have been developing among students, as it is a direct access for language learners to learn vocabulary, and will be necessary for students’ future research because they can benefit more from corpora, and analyze them from a corpus first hand.

To conclude, there are many and many techniques to teach academic vocabulary, searching can be most helpful way to find them both from authentic resources or online tools. Traditional way of teaching on vocabulary could be helpful, but incorporating computer technologies or corpora could be more beneficial as they attract the students’ attention and as a result, they may memorize them easily and effectively.

Moreover, the literature has analyzed the difficulties for EFL learners’ to learn and use academic vocabulary in their daily life. Spending more time on a language and trying to use the words in a context, in other words, by using them actively and adding them in their daily academic discourse could be the solution for their issues on developing their sets of academic wordlist.

The paper widely discussed some controversial ideas of different researchers for approaching to teach academic vocabulary whether online tools or traditional way, related to contexts, could be more beneficial or not. This paper suggests that both of ways, additionally, integrating corpora to study the words would be the most valuable option for teaching academic words effectively.

In Uzbekistan, actually, there could not be enough researches conducted related to teaching academic vocabulary in both spoken and written discourse, especially integrating corpora to the classes. The research paper will continue analyzing to

integrate the ‘Data-driven technique’, specifically using Corpora in the future researches.

REFERENCES:

1. Aldawsari H. 2017, The challenges of learning vocabulary. School of Language and Culture
2. Dobelmann C & Stem A. 2009. Language Boosters. Huntington Beach, CA: Creative Teaching Press
3. Cambridge Advanced Learner’s Dictionary. 2008. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press
4. Joe B., Sunderman G & Schmitt.2011. Lexis. In James Simpson (ed.), The Routledge Handbook of Applied Linguistics, 571-583. Abingdon, UK/New York: Routledge
5. Johns, T. 2002. Data-driven Learning: The perpetual challenge. In B. Ketteman & G. Marko (Eds.), Teaching and learning by doing corpus analysis (pp. 107-117). Amsterdam: Rodopi
6. Lawson M. & Hogben D. 1996. The vocabulary learning strategies of foreign language students. Language Learning 46, 101-135
7. Nation, P. 2001. Learning vocabulary in another Language. Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9781139524759>
8. Nushi M, & Janebzedah H, (2016) Teaching and Learning Academic Vocabulary. Rsearch Gate: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/305072985>
9. Selvestr, M. 2012. Immesive learning in preservice teacher education: Using virtual worlds. The international HETL Review 2, 54-75
10. Hatch E & Cheryl Brown. 1995. Vocabulary, Semantics and Language Education. New York: Cambridge University Press
11. Washburn, P. 2009. The Vocabulary of Critical Thinking. New York: Oxford University Press.